

Research Article

Formulation and Development of Bilayer Tablet for Irritable Bowel Disease

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The objective of the present research was to formulate and develop a bilayer tablet containing Metronidazole and Dicyclomine Hydrochloride for the effective treatment of Irritable Bowel Disease. Metronidazole was incorporated as an immediate-release layer, whereas Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was formulated as a sustained-release layer. The rationale behind combining these two drugs in a bilayer system lies in their therapeutic roles: Metronidazole (immediate release) acts as a potent antibiotic commonly used in antidiarrheal therapy for the treatment of inflammation in the large intestine, while Dicyclomine Hydrochloride (sustained release) is an anticholinergic agent primarily administered for irritable bowel disease. The bilayer design enhances therapeutic efficacy by enabling sequential and controlled drug release profiles suitable for managing irritable bowel disease.

Keywords: Anticholinergic agent, Metronidazole, Dicyclomine Hydrochloride, immediate-release layer, Irritable Bowel Disease, sustained-release layer.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS)

In the last two decades, Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) has gained considerable attention in the health-care field due to its increasingly high prevalence, sometimes debilitating effects and diverse symptom representation. IBS is a chronic functional bowel disorder in which abdominal pain or discomfort is associated with defecation or change in bowel habits often in the absence of detectable structural abnormalities. Bloating, distension and disordered defecation are the commonly associated feature (World Gastroenterology Organization Global guideline, 2009). Usually conventional dosage form produce wide ranging fluctuation in drug concentration in the blood stream and tissues with consequent undesirable toxicity and poor efficiency. This factor such as repetitive dosing and unpredictable absorption led to the concept of controlled drug delivery systems. The goal in designing sustained or controlled delivery systems is to increase effectiveness of the drug by localization at

the site of action and providing uniform drug delivery. Bi-layer tablet is suitable for sequential release of two drugs in combination (Shila V. D. et al, 2013). The first time establish diagnostic criteria to define IBS was made in the 1970s by Manning and colleagues. The Manning and colleagues compared symptoms in patients with abdominal pain who turned out either to have or not to have disease (Manning et al, 1978). Over the past 10 years considerably more attention has been paid to IBS, and the successive Rome working parties have elaborated more detailed, accurate, and useful definitions of the syndrome.

Manning criteria:

1. Pain relieved by defecation
2. More frequent stools at onset of pain
3. Looser stools at onset of pain
4. Visible abdominal distension
5. Passage of mucus per rectum
6. Sense of incomplete evacuation (Spiller R. et al, 2007)

1.2 Symptoms of Irritable Bowel Syndrome

- Symptoms vary and are often associated with food intake and, characteristically, with defecation
- Symptoms interfere with daily life and social functioning in many patients.
- Symptoms sometimes seem to develop as a consequence of an intestinal infection (postinfectious IBS) or to be precipitated by major life events, or occur during a period of considerable stress
- Symptoms may develop abdominal pain and cramping.
- A change in bowel habits, such as diarrhoea.

MATERIAL AND MATERIAL:

Preformulation Studies:

Determination of Melting Point

Take a capillary tube and seal one end by heating it. Fill the capillary tube with drug powder upto 2-3mm high. Put the capillary tube in Melting point apparatus and increase the temperature slowly. Note down the temperature when the drug starts melting and again note the temperature when the drug gets completely melted.

Determination of wavelength using UV spectrophotometric analysis:

50mg of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was weighed and dissolved into 50ml of distilled water to prepare a 1000 μ g/ml stock solution from which a 10 μ g/ml dilution was prepared. Baseline correction was performed using distilled water and sample was run between 200-400nm wavelength range in spectrum mode. 50mg of Metronidazole was weighed and dissolved into 50ml of distilled water to prepare a 1000 μ g/ml stock solution from which a 10 μ g/ml dilution was prepared. Baseline correction was performed using distilled water and sample was run between 200-400nm wavelength range in spectrum mode by using Shimadzu 1800 UV visible spectrophotometer (Jethara S.I. et al, 2012).

Preparation of calibration curves:

The calibration curve of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride were prepared in distilled water and 6.8 pH phosphate buffer by using Shimadzu 1800 UV visible

spectrophotometer. Accurately weighed 50mg of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was transferred into a 50ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with distilled water to obtain a 1000 μ g/ml stock solution of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride. From the stock solution 1ml was taken and transferred into a 10ml volumetric flask and rest of the volume was made up with methanol to obtain a 100 μ g/ml of solution from which 1 to 10 μ g/ml dilutions were prepared. Same procedure was followed for distilled water, phosphate buffer 6.8 to prepare calibration curve respectively. The calibration curve of Metronidazole were prepared in distilled water and 1.8 pH phosphate buffer by using Shimadzu 1800 UV visible spectrophotometer. Accurately weighed 50mg of Metronidazole was transferred into a 50ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with methanol to obtain a 1000 μ g/ml stock solution of Metronidazole. From the stock solution 1ml was taken and transferred into a 10ml volumetric flask and rest of the volume was made up with methanol to obtain a 100 μ g/ml of solution from which 1 to 10 μ g/ml dilutions were prepared. Same procedure was followed for distilled water, phosphate buffer 7.2 to prepare calibration curve respectively (Jethara S.I. et al, 2012).

Determination of solubility of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride in various medium:

The solubility of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride in various medium was determined by shake flask method. In this method 2ml of each solvent was taken into a vial and an excess amount of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was added. The vials were sealed properly and stirred for 10min. They were then kept on orbital flask shaker at 37°C for 24h. After solubilization of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride, an extra amount of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was added to the vials containing drug-solvent mixture. The process was repeated until saturation solubility of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride, indicated by presence of undissolved drug. The mixtures were then kept at room temperature for 24 h. and centrifuged using remi12c micro-centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 15min. The supernatant were separated and diluted with respective solvents. The drug concentration was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 247nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu- 1800).

Determination of solubility of Metronidazole in various medium:

The solubility of Metronidazole in various medium was determined by shake flask method. In this method 2ml of each solvent was taken into a vial and an excess amount of Metronidazole was added. The vials were sealed properly and stirred for 10min. They were then kept on orbital flask shaker at 37°C for 24h. After solubilization of Metronidazole, an extra amount of Metronidazole was added to the vials containing drug-solvent mixture. The process was repeated until saturation solubility of Metronidazole, indicated by presence of undissolved drug. The mixtures were then kept at room temperature for 24 h. and centrifuged using Remi12C micro- centrifuge at 3000RPM for 15min. The supernatant were separated and diluted with respective solvents. The drug concentration was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 274 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1800) (Ryakala H. et al, 2015).

Drug-excipient compatibility study:

The compatibility of the drug was assessed by drug-excipient interaction study. The drug was mixed with various excipients in a 1:1 ratio in glass vials which were properly sealed and kept undisturbed at 40°C temperature for 14 days. After 14 days incompatibility was confirmed by TLC.

Selection of excipients:

- HPMC K4M, Eudragit RLPO and RSPO for combined release profile by combination of HPMC, RL and RSPO in different ratio for delivering a sustain release formulation of Dicyclomine with no interaction of drug and polymer it should be time independent release profile of the drug.
- Microcrystalline cellulose as diluents and bulking agent to increasing a bulk of drug.
- PVP-K30 as binder for make slurry of drug and Excipient to help a wet mass and granule formulation.
- Isopropyl alcohol as solvent for wetting.
- Magnesium stearate as a lubricant for lubrication.
- Talc as glidant.

Formulation and development:

Preparation of Metronidazole Immediate release layer by Direct Compression

- Weigh all Ingredients as per the quantities defined in table no. 6.3
- Pass all the ingredients through sieve #80 and collect individuals in polybags.
- Mix measured quantity of Metronidazole, sodium starch glycolate and PVP-K30 for 15 minutes in a polybag.
- Magnesium stearate and talc was added to it and blend for 5 min in paste mortar.
- Compress final blend using B-Tooling, multiple rotatory compression machine using 8 mm round shaped punches and corresponding dies.

Table no. 6.3 Formula for Immediate release layer

Sr.No.	Ingredients	Quantity
		Per 10 Tablets (in mg)
1.	Metronidazole	2500
2.	Sodium starch glycolate	300
3.	PVP K-30	150
4.	Magnesium Stearate	50
5.	Talc	50

Preparation of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride Sustained release layer by Wet Granulation

- Weigh all Ingredients as per the quantities defined in tablet no. 2.
- Pass all the ingredients through sieve no #80 and collect in separate polybags.

- Prepare binder solution by dissolving PVP-K30 in Isopropyl alcohol.
- Mix all material expect lubricant for 15 min.
- Add binder solution to the above step and mix until uniform dough mass granules are formed.
- Pass all granules through #12 no. sieve.
- Dry all the granules at 50-55°C temperature.

- Add Magnesium stearate and Talc and blend it for 5 Minute.
- Compress final blend using B-tooling, multiple rotatory compression machine using 8 mm round shape punches and corresponding dies.

Selection of polymers and suitable experimental design

The polymers, viz. HPMC K4M, Eudragit RLPO and Eudragit RSPO were selected owing to their releasing rate controlling ability, stability and compatibility with drug. Successful use of polymer is known to

provide the formulation with sustained drug release property. A central composite design for two factor three level was selected to optimize the variable response. The two factors, viz. Sustained release Polymer X1 Eudragit RSPO and Binding agent Polymer X2 PVP-K30 of each polymer blend, were required by the experimental design and the factor level were suitably coded. The amount of Magnesium stearate was kept constant, while Isopropyl alcohol was taken in a sufficient quantity to maintain a constant tablet mass of 200mg. time taken to release 50% of drug were taken as the variable response.

Table no. 6.4 Sustained release layer formula optimization

S.no.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	Dicyclomine Hydrochloride	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
2.	Eudragit RSPO	400	400	400	500	500	500	600	600	600
3.	Microcrystalline cellulose	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800
4.	PVP-K30	80	100	120	80	100	120	80	100	120
5.	Magnesium Stearate	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
6.	Talc	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
7.	Isopropyl alcohol	QS								

Formulation optimization:

a. Variables: These are the measurement, values which are characteristics of data there are two type of variable Dependent variable independent variable, Independent variable are the variable which are not dependent any other value. Lubricant concentration, Polymer ratio, etc. Dependent variable dependent on the concentration of independent variable used.

b. Factor: Factor is assigned variable such as Ratio of polymer grade, Temperature, concentration, Lubricating agent polymer ratio. A quantitative factor has numerical value to it eg. Concentration (1%, 2%,

3%.) Drug polymer ratio (1:1) (1:2) (1:1:1 etc) Qualitative factors which are not numerical. Polymer grade, Humidity condition, type of equipment are discrete nature.

c. Levels: The level of a factor are the values of designation to the factor eg. Concentration 1 % one level while 2% with another level usually level are indicated as low or middle or high level. Normally for ease of calculation the numeric and discrete level low level and high level.

Formula for conversion

$$\text{Level} = \frac{\text{X-the average of the two levels}}{\text{Half of the difference of the level}}$$

d. Responses: Response is mostly represented by the outcome of experiment. It is the effect which are going to evaluate, Disintegration time,

e. Effect: The effect of factor change of the response caused by varying the level of the describe relationship between various factor level.

f. Interaction: It is also similar effect gives overall effect of two or more variables.

Evaluation of Granules

Bulk density

Bulk density is defined as the ratio of mass of the powder to the bulk volume of the powder. 10gm of granules were taken in a 100ml measuring cylinder and noted down the volume occupied by the granules (Reddy B.V. et al, 2015).

Tapped density

Tapped density is defined as the ratio of the mass of the bulk powder to the tapped volume of the powder. 10gm of granules were taken in a 100ml measuring cylinder and noted down the volume occupied by the granules after tapping.

Angle of repose

Angle of repose is a characteristic related to inter-particulate friction. The angle of repose was performed to determine the flow property of the formed granules. Set the funnel 4cm above the working slab. Pour the granule through funnel until pile of granules touches the funnel. Note the height and diameter/radius of the pile of granules. Determine

$$\text{Poured density} = \frac{\text{mass of granules}}{\text{Poured volume of granules}}$$

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{mass of granules}}{\text{Tapped volume of granules}}$$

Determine Hausner's ratio and Carr's Index

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Tablet punching

Switch on the main button. Set the required RPM, thickness and hardness of tablet punching machine. Feed the powders bed in hopper. Press switch (green color) to start compression cycle. Check that die cavity is completely filled by powders bed during rotation. After filling the compression force applied by upper punch and simultaneously tablets ejected by lower punch. These processes continued till die cavity filled properly by powder bed. In case of uneven filling of die cavity stop the compression process (press red switch).

angle of repose by applying the formula (Reddy B.V. et al, 2015).

$$\tan\theta = h/r$$

where θ = angle of repose
h = height of pile
r = radius of pile

Hausner's ratio and carr's index

Flow ability of a powder was evaluated by comparing the bulk density and tapped density of a powder. It is an indication of compressibility of a powder. It measures the relative significance of interparticle interactions. A Hausner's ratio of <1.25 indicates a powder that is free flowing whereas >1.25 indicates poor flow ability of powder (Reddy B.V. et al, 2015). Take 20gm granules in measuring cylinder. Note the poured volume of granules. Now tap it for 100 times. Note the tapped volume of granules. Determine poured density and tapped density by applying the formula.

Evaluation of Bilayer Tablet

Weight variation

Weight individually 20 tablets selected at random. Calculate the average weight. Not more than two of the individual weights deviate from the average weight by more than percentage shown in the table and none deviates by more than twice that percentage. If more than two tablets deviate from the range, retest 20 tablets are done and not more than 2 tablets should deviate from 40 tablets (Kumar E.S. et al, 2014).

Thickness

Set scale to zero. Place the tablet laterally between the jaws of vernier caliper. Make sure jaws shall just touch object to be measured. Record the reading displayed. Take out the sample, clean the jaws and keep the caliper in place.

Hardness

Place the tablet on the holder. Set the "0" on Monsanto tester scale. Press the tablet. The range of Monsanto hardness tester is "0 to 20" kg. When tablet breaks read the pressure applied and Clean the holder.

Friability

Connect the main socket. Weigh the tablets before placing it in friability apparatus. Place 10 tablets in the friability test apparatus. Switch "ON" the mains. Take out tablets after 100 revolutions has completed. Reweigh the tablets after dedusting. Switch "OFF" the mains. Clean the friability test apparatus.

Drug Content

For drug content, one of the tablet was crushed and transferred in 1000 ml of volumetric flask. Make up the volume with phosphate buffer 7.2. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper, Metronidazole and Dicyclomine hydrochloride were analyzed at 274 and 212 nm respectively using U.V. Visible spectrophotometer after suitable dilution.

Invitro drug dissolution study

The invitro drug release was performed according to the USP dissolution apparatus II at 50 rpm and temperature was taken between $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ over 24-hour period for Dicyclomine hydrochloride SR and 1 hour for Metronidazole IR, using an automated paddle dissolution system. A minimum of 6 tablets per batch were tested. Switch ON the mains from electric board. Adjust/maintain temperature from heater knob. Maintain the water level in the water bath up to the specific mark The media used was 0.1 N HCl at a pH

1.2 and followed by phosphate buffer 7.2 was used as dissolution medium and maintained at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The sample of 5 ml was withdrawn at particular time interval and replaced with fresh dissolution media maintained at same temperature and the concentration of dissolved drug was determined using UV Spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 214 for Dicyclomine Hydrochloride and 274 for Metronidazole. Determine the concentration and percentage drug release. Switch OFF heater and main of the apparatus (Kumar E.S. et al, 2014).

Stability studies

The stability studies were carried out for a period of 1 month in the stability chamber. The tablets were stored under the following conditions as prescribed by the ICH guidelines ($40^\circ\text{C}\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\pm 5\%$ RH Q1C). The tablets were withdrawn periodically with an interval of 30 days and analyzed for Weight variation, Hardness, Disintegration, Dissolution, drug content etc (Kumar E.S. et al, 2014).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation

Drug Characterization

Melting point determination:

The melting point of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was found to $165-168^\circ\text{C}$ which is same as reported in literature. The melting point of Metronidazole was found to be $158-164^\circ\text{C}$ which is same as reported in literature.

Determination of wavelength using UV spectrophotometric analysis:

The maximum wavelength of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride was found to be 212.60 nm which matches the reported wavelength.

Figure 7.1 Spectrum of Dicyclomine Hcl

The maximum wavelength of Metronidazole was found to be 274 nm which matches the reported wavelength.

Figure 7.2 Spectrum of Metronidazole

Preparation of calibration curves:

The calibration curves of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride in various solvents e.g. Distilled water, and 7.2 pH phosphate buffer were prepared and shown below:

Table 7.1 Absorbance data of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride in distilled water for preparation of calibration curve, at 212 nm

S. N	Concentration (ug/ml)	Absorbance (mean \pm standard deviation) (n=3)
1	0	0
2	10	0.0213 \pm 0.0045
3	20	0.0360 \pm 0.0050
4	30	0.0540 \pm 0.0077
5	40	0.0703 \pm 0.0095
6	50	0.0930 \pm 0.0108

Figure 7.3 Calibration curve of Dicyclomine Hcl in Distilled water

Table 7.2 Absorbance data of Dicyclomine Hyrdochloride in phosphate buffer 7.2 for preparation of calibration curve, at 214 nm

S.NO.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (mean ± standard deviation) (n=3)
1	0	0
2	10	0.0136±0.004
3	20	0.036±0.0026
4	30	0.0536±0.0051
5	40	0.0703±0.006
6	50	0.0876±0.009

Figure 7.4 Calibration curve of Dicyclomine Hcl in pH 7.2

The calibration curves of Metronidazole in various solvents e.g. Distilled water, and 1.2 pH phosphate buffer were prepared and shown below:

Table 7.3 Absorbance data of Metronidazole in distilled water for preparation of calibration curve, at 274 nm

S.NO.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (mean ± standard deviation) (n=3)
1	0	0
2	2	0.1053±0.0133
3	4	0.2006±0.0128
4	6	0.2843±0.0073
5	8	0.3893±0.0092
6	10	0.4703±0.0073

Figure 7.5 Calibration curve of Metronidazole in Distilled water

Table 7.4 Absorbance data of Metronidazole in phosphate buffer 1.2 pH for preparation of calibration curve, at 274 nm

S.NO.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (mean ± standard deviation) (n=3)
1	0	0
2	2	0.067±0.0157
3	4	0.132±0.0156
4	6	0.2053±0.017
5	8	0.2843±0.017
6	10	0.3659±0.0149

Figure 7.6 Calibration curve of Metronidazole in pH 1.2

Determination of solubility of Dicyclomine Hcl and Metronidazole in various medium:

The solubility of Dicyclomine Hcl and Metronidazole in various mediums were studied and the results of study were shown in below table:

Table 7.5 Solubility data of Dicyclomine Hyrdochloride in different mediums

S.NO.	Solvent	Solubility ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1	Distilled water	0.76 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
4	Phosphate buffer pH 7.2	0.73 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Table 7.6 Solubility data of Metronidazole in different mediums

S.NO	Solvent	Solubility ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) Mean \pm SD
1	Distilled water	0.99 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
4	Phosphate buffer pH 1.2	0.93 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Drug-excipient interaction study:

The drug Dicyclomine Hyrdochloride and Metronidazole was found to be compatible with

various excipients which were selected for formulation of Bilayer Tablet. The compatibility was assessed by TLC and the retention factors of all ratios found similar.

Table 7.7 Data of Drug Excipient interaction study

S. No.	Compound	75% RH, 40 $^{\circ}$ c Stability Chamber			
		15 days	30 days	45 days	Room Temperature
1.	Dicyclomine Hcl + RSPO (1:1)	No change	No change	No change	No change
2.	Dicyclomine Hcl + RLPO (1:1)	No change	No change	No change	No change
3.	Dicyclomine Hcl + HPMC K4M (1:1)	No change	No change	No change	No change
4.	Drugs (Both) + MCC (1:1)	No change	No change	No change	No change
5.	Metronidazole + SSG (1:1)	No change	No change	No change	No change

Formulation and Development

Determination of various flow properties:

Table 7.8 Various flow properties of Sustained release formulation

Characterization	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Bulk density	0.516	0.524	0.514	0.524	0.514	0.524	0.511	0.516	0.524
Tapped density	0.620	0.623	0.618	0.625	0.618	0.625	0.570	0.626	0.623
Carr's index	16.4	16.3	16.6	16.1	16.6	16.1	16.2	16.4	16.3
Hausner's ratio	1.186	1.192	1.201	1.171	1.201	1.171	1.210	1.186	1.192
Angle of repose	26.4	26.2	26.8	26.4	26.8	26.4	26.44	26.4	26.22

Determination of Evaluation of Bi-layer tablet:

The various evaluation parameters were evaluated like thickness, hardness, weight variation, friability,

drug content and the results of the study were shown in below table:

Table 7.9 Evaluation of Bi-layer tablets:

Formulation Batch	Thickness (mm) \pm SD	Weight variation (mg) \pm SD	Hardness (Kg/cm ²) \pm SD	Friability (%) \pm SD	Drug Content (%)	
					Metronidazole	Dicyclomine Hcl
F1	6.33 \pm 0.057	517.33 \pm 4.04	5.03 \pm 0.057	0.26 \pm 0.011	98.86 \pm 0.152	98.40 \pm 0.503
F2	6.33 \pm 0.115	511.0 \pm 2.64	5.36 \pm 0.404	0.26 \pm 0.011	98.48 \pm 0.355	98.34 \pm 1.270
F3	6.83 \pm 0.057	506.0 \pm 2.64	5.23 \pm 0.057	0.23 \pm 0.036	99.16 \pm 0.567	98.67 \pm 0.629
F4	6.66 \pm 0.230	513.33 \pm 0.57	4.86 \pm 0.305	0.26 \pm 0.015	98.24 \pm 0.673	97.58 \pm 0.51
F5	6.93 \pm 0.057	521.66 \pm 1.15	5.4 \pm 0.057	0.18 \pm 0.057	99.81 \pm 0.045	99.79 \pm 0.180
F6	6.86 \pm 0.057	523.0 \pm 2.64	5.3 \pm 0.115	0.19 \pm 0.057	99.79 \pm 0.015	99.79 \pm 0.081
F7	6.7 \pm 0.1	514.0 \pm 2.64	5.2 \pm 0.230	0.26 \pm 0.057	98.60 \pm 0.522	97.81 \pm 0.229
F8	6.63 \pm 0.057	519.33 \pm 3.05	4.5 \pm 0.264	0.29 \pm 0.03	98.32 \pm 0.347	97.99 \pm 0.825
F9	6.63 \pm 0.115	514.33 \pm 6.50	5.3 \pm 0.360	0.27 \pm 0.025	98.70 \pm 0.512	98.16 \pm 0.704

In-vitro drug release study for sustained formulation: The percentage drug release from sustained release were found to be 93.51%

Table 7.10 Percentage drug release data of Sustained release Tablet

S. No.	Time (in min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.	5	5.53	1.93	7.33	6.66	4.86	11.61	5.53	1.71	7.78
3.	15	8.68	6.66	10.93	8.01	12.28	15.43	7.11	4.41	11.38
4.	30	14.76	12.28	16.11	9.81	19.93	20.61	11.16	10.93	17.01
5.	45	15.43	20.38	23.53	12.28	27.36	24.66	16.11	18.81	20.61
6.	60	18.81	24.43	32.76	17.23	37.71	34.11	25.11	20.38	26.68
7.	120	37.26	25.11	50.31	33.66	41.31	43.33	47.61	32.76	40.86
8.	180	52.11	26.46	53.68	37.93	47.83	50.53	57.28	41.53	52.78
9.	240	55.03	45.81	61.11	49.86	51.88	63.13	62.68	50.53	61.56
10.	360	56.16	49.86	64.71	55.93	79.11	76.18	68.53	63.36	64.93
11.	480	67.18	63.81	84.96	61.56	93.51	89.91	72.36	64.93	72.81

Figure 7.7 Percentage drug release from Sustained release formulation.

Stability studies

The bilayer tablet of Metronidazole and Dicyclomine Hydrochloride were prepared and subject to stability studies as per ICH guidelines for one month in stability chamber at 40°C at 75% RH. The subjected tablets was found to have no change in physical appearance and drug content.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Formulation of Bilayer tablet of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride and Metronidazole for the treatment of Irritable bowel disease was done in which at primary stage we studied and work on the literature reviews of various research and review articles regarding bilayer tablet and correlated disease then in next step working on formulation so we studied various excipient and there action after selection of excipient we select method of manufacturing. In formulation part primary performing preformulation in which drug identity, solubility and compatibility was done. Compatibility of study was done in different ratios of polymer and was putted in stability chamber for 45 days at 37°C temperature and 75% RH and observe the physical appearance of drug and Excipient. For the production of sustained release layer formulate different ratio of Eudragit RLPO, RSPO, and HPMC K4M and release rate study was done. The bilayer tablet was punched using rotatory punching machine and evaluation of tablet was done in which weight variation, Thickness, Hardness, friability, drug content, disintegration and invitro dissolution was performed. In present work bilayer tablet was formulated in which Metronidazole will provide a fast release to show an immediate effect on diarrhea and other layer of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride will provide a sustained release of drug and will useful for the prolonged action on spasm produce in irritable bowel disease. The simulatenous medication of diarrhea and abdominal pain in the condition of irritable bowel disease was provided by these formulations. The major advantage of formulation will be reduction of dosing frequency and enhancement of patient compliance and therapeutic effect. In present work we formulate a bilayer tabet of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride and Metronidazole and it is helpful for patient and next generation.

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